

MB and Tsallis Distributions, MaxEnt and the Notion of Moments of e/T

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In statistical mechanics, particularly in the derivation of the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis distributions (see (1)), there is a major emphasis on maximizing an entropy function subject to constraints. It is assumed that the probability is a function of e_i/T (single particle energy divided by temperature) and so these constraints are often moments of e_i/T , usually the zeroth and first moments. Furthermore, the entropy function is also expressed as an average of a particular function $F(p(e_i))$. In the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, $F(p(e_i)) = -\ln(p(e_i))$.

The point we make is that if one statistically describes a system, a priori, by average moments, then writing an average of a function $F(p(e_i))$ means that this function may be written as a power series of e_i . It is inconsistent to argue that the $F(p(e_i))$ can have more moments than the moments used in the constraints as both schemes ultimately should use the same average moments of e_i/T to statistically describe the same system. We suggest that this is a key underlying idea to finding MB and Tsallis solutions. We try to generalize the maximization problem and show that there are at least three distinct solutions based on the moment idea. One is $F(p) = \ln(p)$ (MB case) and two others are Tsallis distributions. In one case, $p(e_i)$ is the probability, while in the other case, we generalize to $g(p(e_i))$, where only $p(e_i)$ is normalized.

MaxEnt Approaches

Maximum entropy approaches involve maximizing a function $G(p(e_i))$ subject to constraints. What are these constraints? They are often moments of e_i/T with $p(e_i/T)$ being a normalized probability. In particular, the zeroth and first moments of e_i/T are used. $G(p(e_i))$, however, is completely unknown. The next step is to write:

$$G(p(e_i)) = g(p(e_i)) F(p(e_i)) \text{ with } g(p(e_i)) > 0 \quad ((1))$$

The simplest case is $g(p(e_i)) = p(e_i)$, but in principle one could have $g(p(e_i))$ being a different function and also being unnormalized. We discuss this in more detail later. ((1)) is written as an average of the function $F(p(e_i))$. One may ask: Why would one wish to do this? Does it provide for a solution in any manner? We argue that it does in the following way. The constraints represent the zeroth and first moments of e_i/T and so ((1)), with $F(p(e_i))$ expanded as a power series in e_i/T must represent the same moments. The average ((1)) is a statistical description of the system and cannot contain information about more moments than the set used for the constraints. In other words:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i e_i p(e_i) = \langle e_i \rangle \quad (\text{or } \sum_i e_i g(p(e_i)) = \langle e_i \rangle) \quad ((2a))$$

is a statistical description of the system in terms of moments of e_i .

$$\sum_i g(p(e_i)) F(p(e_i)) \quad ((2b))$$

Is an equivalent description of the system and as the system is described by moments of e_i , then $F(p(e_i))$ should only contain the same moments which appear in the constraints. Otherwise, one has two different statistical descriptions of the same system. This means that:

$$F(p(e_i)) = a e_i + b \quad ((3))$$

((3)) is a key result which applies to both the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis descriptions. In a general maximization problem, even writing ((1)), there would be no reason to impose ((3)). The maximization of entropy is really about an information function directly linked to moments used in averages which ultimately statistically describe the system.

Given the form ((3)), we suggest that there are at least three math solutions which allow for a maximization of ((1)) subject to constraints, consistent with the idea of moments.

Three Solutions Based on MaxEnt and Moments

If one has $p(e_i)$ representing the probability to have a particle with e_i , then this normalized probability may be used to calculate averages of moments of e_i . It is possible, however, that $p(e_i)$ (normalized) depends on e_i , but is not the probability to have an e_i . Such a probability is

$$g(p(e_i)) \text{ where } g(p) \text{ may not be normalized } ((4))$$

As an example, consider a set $p(e_i)$ with $g(p(e_i)) = p(e_i)^q$. If $p(e_i)$ sums to 1, then unless $q=1$,

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ } g(p(e_i)) \neq 1 \quad ((5))$$

For $q>1$, each $p(e_i)<1$ becomes even smaller and the sum is less than 1.

For $q<1$, each $p(e_i)$ may be thought of as related to $1/n$ and $\sqrt[n]{n}<n$, so $1/n < 1/\sqrt[n]{n}$ meaning that $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } g(p(e_i))>1$. ((6))

Thus, one considers the maximization of:

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ } g(p(e_i)) F(p(e_i)) + a \text{ Sum over } i \text{ } e_i g(p(e_i)) + b \text{ Sum over } i \text{ } p(e_i) \quad ((7))$$

In general, one does not focus on the form of $F(p(e_i))$ based on the moments of e_i used in the constraints, but we suggest that this is the key to finding solutions because $g(p(e_i)) F(p(e_i))$ is in the form of an average and may be expanded in terms of the sum of averages of moments of e_i .

In particular, in (1), the Tsallis $F(p(e_i))$ is assumed a priori, i.e.

$$F(p(e_i)) = \{e_i^{1-q} - 1\} / (1-q) \quad ((8))$$

The MaxEnt process in (1) is then:

$$\text{Maximize: } - \sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i)) - (a-1) \sum_i (p(e_i)-1) - b \sum_i p(e_i)(e_i - \text{eave}) \quad ((9))$$

$$\text{The solution is } \exp_q((-a-be_i)/(2-q)) \quad ((9))$$

We point out, however, that in general one would not know the form ((8)) a priori when maximizing ((9)). We suggest that one should start with a general $F(p(e_i))$ subject to the moment rule ((2a)) and ((2b)). This means that:

$$F(p(e_i)) = a + be_i \text{ a priori } ((10)) \text{ and:}$$

$$dg/dp(e_i) (a + be_i) + g(p) dF/dp(e_i) = a_1 e_i dg/dp(e_i) + a_2 \quad ((11))$$

The RHS side is based on the zeroth and first moments of e_i . For the e_i average, $g(p(e_i))$ is used, but for the a_2 term, one uses

$$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \text{ because } \sum_i g(p(e_i)) \text{ is not necessarily } 1 \quad ((12))$$

One is interested in moments of e_i .

If $g(p) = p$, then there is an e_i moment from $dg/dp = b e_i$ on the LHS and $a_1 e_i dg/dp$ on the RHS.

$$g(p) dF/dp = p dF/dp = a_3 e_i + b_3 \quad ((13))$$

If one considers F as a power series of p , the dF/dp is in general a different function than F . There is a solution, however, which yields

$$p dF/dp = b_3 \text{ namely } F = \ln(p) \quad ((14))$$

$$\text{Alternatively, one could have } p dF/dp = a_4 + b_4 e_i \quad ((15))$$

$$\text{This means that if } F = z_1 + z_2 p^{\text{power}(1-q)}, \text{ then } p dF/dp = z_3 F(p) = c_1 + c_2 e_i \quad ((16))$$

This is also a satisfactory solution, i.e. a Tsallis solution. If one wishes $F_q(p)$ to become $\ln(p)$ for $q=1$, then:

$$F(p) = (1 - p^{\text{power}(1-q)}) / (1-q) \quad ((17))$$

If $g(p) \neq p$, then one has an extra $dg/dp = a$ on the LHS of ((11)) unless $a=0$. One may let

$g(p) \frac{dF}{dp} = \text{constant}$ which suggests a power law for $g(p) = p^{\text{power } q}$ and $F(p) = \text{constant} + p^{\text{power } (1-q)}$.

This again leads to the Tsallis solution. If one wishes $F_q(p) = \ln(p)$ for $q=1$, then

$$F(p) = (1 - p^{\text{power } (1-q)}) / (1-q) \quad ((18))$$

Thus, there are two ways, based on the method of moments of e_i/T , to obtain the Tsallis distribution, and one way to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that while one may obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis distributions via MaxEnt subject to constraints, what one seems to be doing with the constraints is describe the statistical system in terms of average moments of e_i/T . If one writes the function to be maximized as $p(e)F(p(e_i))$ or $g(p(e_i)) F(p(e_i))$, where $g(p(e_i))$ is the probability used to calculate the e_i moment (with $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ being the zeroth), then this is also a statistical description which must be compatible with the constraints. Therefore, it cannot contain more e_i/T moments. This means that $F(p(e_i)) = a + be_i$ which already gives much information about F . We show that one may find three mathematical solutions, two linked with the Tsallis distribution and one with the Maxwell-Boltzmann.

References

1. Trindade, M. Information theoretic structure for Tsallis q -entropy in statistical physics (2026)
<https://www.semanticscholar.org/reader/4078c5abbfb1a1e387fc00110517dc065fc24862>